

EQUALITY BEYOND REACH? A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF ARTICLE 45 OF THE CONSTITUTION IN THE CONTEXT OF MATRIMONIAL PROPERTY IN KENYA.

“Having considered the issue, we find that the applicant has established that there is uncertainty in the law arising from contrary views in the High Court and in the Court of Appeal which requires clarification. More importantly and of concern, is whether Article 45 (3) provides for proprietary rights and whether the said article can be a basis for apportionment and division of matrimonial property without parties fulfilling their obligation of proof what they are entitled to by way of contribution. There is a concern that Article 45 talks about equality and cannot and should not be used as a distribution matrix of matrimonial property. Again, whether Article 45 (3) can be or is a ticket for 50-50 distribution has to be sorted out by the Supreme Court. In our view, the matters raised by the applicant are not only weighty and substantial but completely transcend the dispute between the parties herein. These are so fundamental, that the Supreme Court ought to have a bite.¹

It is against this background that I shall seek to analyze the Constitutional provision under Article 45(3) and how it relates to the division of the matrimonial property in the event of dissolution of marriage. More importantly, the question of whether equality guaranteed under Article 45 of the Constitution connotes the sharing of matrimonial property on a 50-50 basis shall be addressed.

INTRODUCTION

When the ship of marriage hits the rock, flounders and sinks either through separation or divorce there arises the issues of division of matrimonial property. The constitution of Kenya 2010, the *grund norm*, provides for the rights and interests of individuals when it comes to ownership of property in Kenya. Property division laws in Kenya can be confusing for those going through separation especially for the first time. Different states use different division laws when it comes to divorce. Some countries operate under the principle of equitable distribution. This does not necessarily mean that the property is distributed equally among the spouses rather it is awarded to the spouse that earned it.

¹ Court of Appeal in *JOO v MBO [2020] eKLR*

Kenya's matrimonial property division legal regime borrows heavily from England.² However, with the promulgation of the new Constitution in 2010, there was a significant paradigm shift in the area of matrimonial property law. The question that should come to our minds when discussing this should be, what then is a matrimonial property? The matrimonial property act defines matrimonial property as:

(a) the matrimonial home or homes; (b) household goods and effects in the matrimonial home or homes; or (c) any other immovable and movable property jointly owned and acquired during the subsistence of the marriage (2) Despite subsection (1), trust property, including property held in trust under customary law, does not form part of matrimonial property. (3) Despite subsection (1), the parties to an unintended marriage may enter into an agreement before their marriage to determine their property rights. (4) A party to an agreement made under subsection (3) may apply to the Court to set aside the agreement and the Court may set aside the agreement if it determines that the agreement was influenced by fraud, coercion or is manifestly unjust.³

A home purchased before marriage to be a family house is an exception to this case. Pre-marital assets, gifts and inherited property are also excluded from being matrimonial property. Therefore, for a property to be declared as a matrimonial property it must constitute a matrimonial home.

1.1. Laws governing the division of matrimonial property in Kenya.

Laws on the division of matrimonial property have been inconsistently applied by judges who lack legislative parameters within which to ascertain the critical issues such as contribution, needs and resources of separating couples. Admittedly, there has been ambiguity, inconsistency as well as uncertainty with regard to the laws governing matrimonial property. At the same time, varied interpretation especially in Kenya when it comes to division of matrimonial property has or at least did exist. Should the matrimonial property be shared based on one's contribution or should it be shared equally irrespective of one's contribution?

1.2. The 2010 constitution

² As is most of Kenyan Statutes.

³ *The matrimonial property act 2013. Section 6*

Promulgation of the new constitution ushered in a new error for Kenyan women, especially during separation time. The people are guided by the national values and principles of governance which include human dignity, social justice, inclusiveness, equality, human rights, non-discrimination and protection of the marginalized⁴. This imposes a duty on decision-makers and legislators to protect and promote equality for both men and women. Adoption of the 2010 constitution brought forth more developments in the jurisprudence of distribution of matrimonial property. It culminates the property rights. The 2010 Constitution, over and above its extensive guarantee of gender equality, specifically provides for the equality of the parties to a marriage, and their entitlement to equal rights during the existence of marriage and even at its dissolution. The constitution provides that in light of Article 65 individuals have the right, either individually or in association with others to acquire and own property.⁵

1.3. Interpretation of Article 45(3) as regards to division of matrimonial property.

Matrimonial property

The 2010 constitution is the supreme law of the land and it forms an integral part of this essay because its promulgation came and provided for the rights and interests of individuals when it comes to ownership of property in marriage. Parties to a marriage are entitled to equal rights at the time of the marriage, during marriage and at the dissolution of marriage.⁶This particular article is the basis of this essay as many questions have arisen as to what it means by parties having equal rights in marriage and the relation it has with ownership of property in marriage.

This very clause is not clear whether the Constitution alludes to a 50/50 division of matrimonial property or whether 'equality' means the contribution of each party in the acquisition of such property. This ambiguity provides a leeway for the exposure of spouses to harsh cultural and judicial decisions that leave them miserable at the dissolution of marriage. The judges are mandated to provide an interpretation to such statements that cause a difficulty in understanding them. Interpretation is the process that which a document is attributed its meaning and words that are used. Constitutional provisions should be construed purposively and contextually. Courts are

⁴ *The constitution of Kenya 2010. Art 10(2)*

⁵ *The constitution of Kenya 2010. Art 40 (1)*

⁶ *The constitution of Kenya 2010. Art 45(3)*

not to impose a meaning that a text is not reasonably capable of bearing. The rights and responsibilities of spouses in relation to the matrimonial property act are purposively connected to article 45 must be purposively interpreted because of its umbilical link to the constitution. We are supposed to identify the mischief that is being sought to be remedied and therefore it is important to pay attention to the historical background of the legislation.

1.4. Does Article 45 provide for proprietary rights and can it be used as a basis for apportionment and division of matrimonial property without proof of what one is entitled to?

We, first of all, have to understand what is meant by parties having equal rights in marriage. Does equality in this essence mean that parties are to share everything in marriage? The court must interpret what the constitution is intended to mean. In my view, the rights enumerated under Article 45 demand equality between parties whenever any dispute arises concerning the matrimonial property.

Justice Kiage JA gives us a brief insight into what is meant by equal rights in marriage in the case of *Agnes Nanjala v Jacob Petrus*.⁷ He states that:

To examine in detail the question of marriage equality as captured in Article 45 (3) of the Constitution. To my mind, all that the Constitution declares is that marriage is a partnership of equals. No spouse is superior to the other. In those few words, all forms of gender superiority-whether taking the form of open or subtle chauvinism, misogyny, violence, exploitation or the like have no place. They restate essentially the equal dignity and right of men and women within the marriage compact. It is not a case of master and servant.⁸

This means that one is not to ride rough shoulders over the rights of the other. One is not to be a mere appendage covered into silence by the sheer might of the other flowing only from that other's gender. The provision gives equal voice and is meant to actualize the voluntariness of

⁷ *Agnes Nanjala Williams v Jacob Petrus Nicholas (2012) eKLR*

⁸ Above

marriage and to hold inviolate the liberty of the marital space. So, in decision making; from what shall be had for dinner to how many children shall be borne, to where the family shall reside or invest-all the way to who shall have custody of children and who shall keep what in the unfortunate event of marital breakdown, the parties are equal in the eyes of the law.

Many people even our legislators tend to misinterpret this provision when they equate it to mean that the rights being discussed are those of sharing matrimonial property equally. In the case of *Federation of Women Lawyers Kenya (FIDA) v AG and another*⁹ where the petitioner challenged the constitutionality of section 7 of the matrimonial property act as she averred that it contravened the provision of article 45 of the constitution of Kenya on equality of spouses in marriage. She further stated that the section infringes the rights of women to own matrimonial property as they have to prove their contribution.

In my view, the petitioner did misinterpret and/ or miscomprehend what equality means in the context of sharing matrimonial property. The provisions of sections 2,6 and 7 of the Act enumerate the rights that are provided by article 45 *verbatim* while, at the same time, recognizing both types of contribution and taking them into account. At the dissolution of a marriage, each partner walks away with what he or she deserves and this must be arrived at by considering their respective contribution.

It is no surprise that this case was dismissed for the reason that sharing matrimonial property equally would open an avenue for parties to get into marriage and walk out of it in the event of divorce with more than they deserve. Therefore, marital equality as provided for by the constitution does not mean the matrimonial property ought to be shared equally during the dissolution of marriage. Equal rights do not mean sharing property in half. If the legislators will interpret this particular clause in the way the petitioner in the FIDA case tends to look at it then it means that this clause will be a creation of potential frauds of those who want to reap from where they did not sow or rather it would be creating a loophole for goal diggers in the society. If one partner does not invest anything in marriage, they are not entitled to ask any slice from what is invested by the other partner based on love.

⁹ *Federation of Women Lawyers Kenya (FIDA) v Attorney General & another [2018] eKLR*

WHAT IS THE MATRIX IN DISTRIBUTION OF MATRIMONIAL PROPERTY?

2.1. Should Article 45 (3) of the constitution be used as a distribution matrix?

The distribution of matrimonial property should not be metricized. Division of matrimonial property need not have a mathematical formula in law rather, it needs to be based on fairness and conscience. We need to do away with the 50-50 ratio. As Kiage J reiterates, “One does not get justice by simply it being served cutting up a contested object of love, ambition and desire into two halves.”¹⁰ The division of the property must be decided after weighing the peculiar circumstances of each case. “It is axiomatic that the division of matrimonial property under Section 112 of the Act is not and, by its very nature cannot be a precise mathematical exercise.”¹¹.

2.2. Is Article 45(3) a ticket for 50-50 sharing of matrimonial property?

Even though the provision relates to the equality of parties to a marriage, it does not necessarily mean that the matrimonial property should be shared equally. In *E.G.M v B.M.M*¹², for instance, Justice Musyoka decision that equality of spouses provided under Article 45 of the Constitution gives spouses an automatic 50% share of the matrimonial property is bad in law and should be reviewed and subsequently quashed. The learned judge, in this case, erred in law when he misinterpreted Article 45 as one that gives an automatic gate pass for a 50% share of the matrimonial property. Furthermore, it should not be used as an avenue for early richness by men who want to reap from rich women and women who see married men adieu to property.

In *Agnes Wanjala v Jacob Petrus*¹³ the court held that Article 45 (3) of the Constitution provides that parties to a marriage are entitled to equal rights at the time of the marriage during the marriage and the dissolution of the marriage.¹⁴ The article gives the parties equal rights in marriage and it argues that the property may be shared 50-50 if the marriage ship sinks. The correct position is that equality in marriage does not equate to an equal share of matrimonial property. The learned judge further stated that:

¹⁰ Justice Kiage in *Federation of Women Lawyers Kenya (FIDA) v Attorney General & another* [2018] eKLR on metricizing matrimonial property

¹¹ See *LOCK YENG FUN v CHUA HOCK CHYE* [2007] SGCA 33

¹² *E.G.M v M.B.B civil appeal* (2020) eKLR

¹³ Ibid

¹⁴ Ibid

In case of dissolution of the marriage, each partner should walk away with what he/she deserves. What one deserves must be arrived at by considering her/his respective contribution whether it be monetary or non-monetary. But to hold that Article 45(3) decrees an automatic 50:50 sharing could imperil the marriage institution.¹⁵

His view was that this would give a chance to fortune seekers to contract marriage and then sit back without contributing to it, later on, they cause discomfort in the union wait to reap the property. This should never be the essence of equality as provided by the article.

In *PWK vs. JKG*, the Court of Appeal stated:

We think that this is an appropriate case where, subject to what we shall say hereafter, a distribution of 50:50 would have been appropriate. This would not be on account of any compelling legal principle that spouses must share equally in matrimonial property but rather, as was succinctly put in *Echaria case* Undoubtedly, it is reasonable to apply the maxim in a case where there have been very substantial contributions otherwise than by way of advancement, by one spouse to the purchase of property in the name of the other spouse but the portion borne by the contributions to the total purchase price or cost is difficult to fix. But if it is plain that the contributing spouse has contributed about one quarter.¹⁶

It was the courts thinking that they were not obliged to award either party half or anything and respected the views of the principles set out in the *Echaria case*¹⁷ as good law and contribution as the basis for distribution of matrimonial property should remain valid.

Suffice to note that the division of property between spouses on a 50-50 basis would result in injustice in the sense that one spouse would be unfairly denied their due share and the other would be enriched beyond their contribution, thereby infringing on one party's rights. The equality of spouses concerning property means that their entitlement thereto must be measured to their respective contributions. Accordingly, the contribution is a key determinant of ownership or

¹⁵ Ibid

¹⁶ *PWK V JKG CIVIL APEAL NO.30 OF (2014) eKLR*

¹⁷ *Peter Mburu Echaria v Priscilla Njeri Echaria [2007] eKLR*

interest of each spouse in the property, whether matrimonial or otherwise.

2.3. Married Women Properties Act (the MWPA)

The married women property is applicable in Kenya by virtue of Section 3 of the Judicature Act which contains important insights to be taken into account in the division of matrimonial property between spouses. The Act provides that “in any question between husband and wife as to the title to or possession of property either party may apply for an order to the court and the Judge may make such order with respect to the property in dispute as he thinks fit.”¹⁸. Under the Act, judges were given the mandate and power to provide statutory justification for doing what was thought to be just between the parties without having regard to the technicalities of property law. This section of the act recognizes indirect contributions to the property. Kenya still relies on section 17 of the MWPA even though they are still in dilemma or rather unable to respond to the inequities caused by the approach of this section. The question is whether indirect contributions alone may suffice for orders under Section 17.¹⁹

In *Miller v Miller*²⁰ it was held that any law that advocates for the division of matrimonial property based on proved contribution alone run counter to the spirit embodied in the Maputo Protocols and at the division of matrimonial property must be affected having due regards to the principle of equality.²¹ The Maputo provisions are that men and women are to have an equitable share of joint property acquired during the existence of their marriage.

2.4. Matrimonial property act 2013

This act was enacted by the parliament as a result of successful amendments by the majority of parliamentarians. Its enactment came at the time when the country needed laws that would attend to issues concerning matrimonial property. From the outset, the preamble asserts that the legislation is an Act of Parliament to provide for the rights and responsibilities of spouses in relation to matrimonial property and connected purposes.

¹⁸ *Married women property act. Section 17*

¹⁹ *Ibid*

²⁰ *Below*

²¹ *Miller v Miller (2006) UKHL 24*

The initial clause before the amendment was based on the reasoning of the ownership of matrimonial property shall be deemed to vest in the spouses in equal shares irrespective of the contribution of either of them towards the acquisition thereof, and shall be divided accordingly upon the occurrence of divorce or dissolution of the marriage provided that in appropriate circumstances a determination can be made during the subsistence of the marriage. Contribution is defined by the act to mean monetary and non-monetary contributions. Non-monetary contribution includes Domestic work and management of the matrimonial home; Child care; Companionship; Management of family business or property; and Farm work²². This section makes a legal opinion of the economic value of unpaid care workers which is mostly done by women. What if the same work was done by a man will this sentiment be considered too?

This was laid down in the case of *Kivuitu v. Kivuitu*²³ case where the court of appeal held that in determining the wife's contribution, the court should consider the indirect contribution of a housewife who devotes her time to keeping the house going while the husband pursues his career of paid employment or self-employment. The *Kivuitu* case has brought out the view that the wife's non-monetary contribution was to be taken into account and value put on it. The court laid down the rule that where property acquired during coventures is registered jointly, it shall be presumed to be held in equal shares. The burden of proof is left at the discretion of the women. They are entitled to equal shares of the property in divorce provided she can prove that the property being contested upon was acquired during the existence of their marriage and that she was able to contribute towards it either directly or indirectly. In this case, the appellant was to put forth or rather prove her contribution to the marriage. She was not able to show her non-monetary contribution in the acquisition of matrimonial property despite the evidence that was adduced.

Conclusion

Two schools of thought were contested in the aforesaid case on the question of equality as provided for under article 45(3) of the constitution. At first, it was thought to mean to be a 50-50, mathematical computation and another was that each party was entitled to the matrimonial property regardless of the contribution and the mode of contribution not being proved. It is my

²² *Matrimonial property act 2013.section 2*

²³ *Kivuitu v kivuitu civil no.23(2004)*

thought that the government ought to harmonize laws governing matrimonial property. There is a need to provide a standard and fair system of division of property that provides security for all parties during marriages and at the dissolution of marriage. No one should reap where they did not sow or no one should reap more than they planted.

It is a matter of concern to interrogate the issue of division of matrimonial property and consider the realist approach. There also need to be guidelines on how non-monetary contribution should be assessed and valued putting in mind all the unrecognized roles and contributions in families by both parties to promote marriage equality. When the marriage ship sinks, it is submitted, the matrimonial property distribution should be based on one's contribution and not to be romantically clutched onto the 50/50 ratio. There should be prenuptial agreements that ensure certain assets remain separate in the event of divorce. Perhaps the time is ripe to consider the prenuptial agreement in Kenya.